

SIX QUESTIONS REGARDING LASER VEIN TREATMENT

The **vein treatment** utilizes Endovenous laser treatment[EvLT] technology is called EvLT treatment. Most of the health insurance plans cover the EvLT treatment. This enables all kinds of men and women to get rid of throbbing, aching, and unsightly veins without having leg vein surgery such as vein stripping. This treatment does not require a lengthy recovery and it is easy and quick too.

The satisfaction of patients with EvLT [vein treatment near me](#) is high. Under local anesthesia, it can be performed on an outpatient basis. This has the following advantages:

- Downtime is little
- Discomfort is minimal
- Procedure time is short
- Aesthetic results are excellent

Who is eligible for Laser vein treatments?

If you are going to seek vein treatment when you are suffering from the aching and cramping of your legs, then the **vein specialist** will arrange ultrasound testing for you. This non-invasive mapping will be performed in the office. The affected saphenous veins are clearly visible in the ultrasound procedure. On the day of treatment, your doctor will provide you the treatment map.

What kind of veins can be treated?

According to a **vein doctor**, this treatment is for the greater saphenous veins. For the development of most varicose veins, this major vein of the leg is responsible. This is the best alternative for the traditional stripping surgery of the greater saphenous veins.

How it will proceed?

To make the treatment virtually painless, a local anesthetic will be applied to the length of your vein on the day of your laser **vein treatment new jersey**. Near the knee, a thin laser fiber will be inserted through a very small point with the help of ultrasound technology. After insertion, it will target the varicose veins wall and with the laser energy, it will close the vein. This will cause the re-routing of the blood. This procedure only requires 1-3 hours. After getting this laser treatment you can resume your daily activity. It will be performed in an outpatient setting.

What happens after the treatment?

The doctor at **varicose vein treatment new jersey** says that you will resume your normal routine. You must do walking for the next 3-4 days. You may slightly experience tightness and bruising on the treated leg. In just a few days, any discomfort should lessen. Compression stockings during the daytime are recommended for at least two weeks

Does EvLT can be covered in the insurance?

The cost of the ultrasound mapping sessions is covered by most health insurance plans. It will also cover a large percentage of the cost of the endovenous laser treatments. It mostly depends on your health care policy. Any fees associated with sclerotherapy for cosmetic refinement are not included in this plan. You may need to speak with [vein treatment near me new jersey](#) to make sure you are pre-approved.

Will my all veins be gone?

There are two types of saphenous veins present in each leg- a smaller vein and a larger vein. The larger veins can cause blood pooling, itching, and cramping in your legs that can only be treated by surgery. While sclerotherapy is being used in treating smaller varicose veins.